

PROFESSOR KASIMOV'S ROLE IN HEALTH CARE AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH ON INTERNAL DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

The contribution of teachers-coaches in raising the young generation, who are the owners of independence, to be educated, literate, spiritually mature and physically healthy is huge. The thorough knowledge and exemplary upbringing provided by them serve as a foundation for the boys and girls who are on the threshold of a great life to become patriots and real people in life, to serve our country and people honestly and selflessly. The services of teachers who have given their knowledge, talent and life for the perfection of humanity have been respected and honoured by people in all times.

Introduction: In 1976-1980, the head of the Department of Internal Diseases Propedeutics, doctor of medical sciences, professor Kasimov Erkin Yuldashevich. Erkin Yoldoshevich Kasimov (1933-2007) is a candidate of medical sciences, a professor, a health worker who served in the Republic of Uzbekistan. He graduated from the Tashkent State Medical Institute in 1957. In 1967, he defended his candidate's thesis. In 1990, he was awarded the scientific title of professor. Author of more than 500 scientific articles. In 1984-1991, he was the chief physician of the Central Clinical Hospital No. 1 of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and since 1990, he has been the head. 2 Department of propaedeutics of internal medicine of ToshMI.

Methodology: Scientific studies have been conducted on the problem of early manifestation and treatment of heart and liver damage in patients with chronic alcoholism. Much attention was paid to the pathogenesis, clinical course of the liver syndrome in chronic colitis, and specific features of the course of cardiovascular and gastrointestinal diseases in the elderly and elderly

people in the conditions of Uzbekistan. Many students and doctors are familiar with the monograph "Identification of heart diseases (difficulties of specific and differential diagnosis)" co-authored by I.Yu. Kasimov. He trained 6 doctors of science and 31 candidates of science.

Discussion: The teacher leaves an imperceptible but very important mark in the life of every person after him. This one word contains a whole world of meaning and respect. The fact that famous people reach the highest heights is also an incomparable effort of teachers.

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